

chloride ($1.073 \times 10^{-2} M$) were prepared and standardised with EDTA and dimethylglyoxime respectively.

(A) 5 ml. palladium chloride solution ($1.147 \times 10^{-2} M$) was diluted to about 25 ml. with distilled water and acidified with about 5 ml conc. hydrochloric acid. To this solution a sufficient excess of alcoholic solution of the reagent (1%, 5 ml.) was added. The precipitates were digested on a water bath for half an hour and filtered through a weighed sintered glass crucible (G_3 or G_4) washed with hot water and aqueous ethanol (1 : 1) and dried at 110° to constant weight.

(B) Gravimetric determination of Pd(II) at different pH:

In order to study the pH ranges over which palladium could be completely precipitated by these reagents the determination was carried out in solutions at different pH adjusted by using dilute hydrochloric acid or dilute sodium hydroxide solution. The results are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—QUANTITATIVE DETERMINATION OF Pd(II) AT DIFFERENT pH

Reagent	pH	Pd(II) taken mg.	Pd(II) chelate mg.	Pd(II) found mg.	Error mg.
I	0.70	6.105	43.10	6.110	+0.006
	0.70	12.210	86.05	12.200	-0.010
	2.45	6.105	43.07	6.105	0.000
	2.45	12.210	86.09	12.210	0.000
	4.20	6.105	43.08	6.105	0.000
	4.20	12.210	86.10	12.210	0.000
	7.00	6.105	43.10	6.110	+0.005
	7.00	12.210	86.00	12.200	-0.010
	10.70	6.105	43.08	6.105	0.000
	10.70	12.210	86.10	12.210	0.000
II	0.70	6.105	44.60	6.094	-0.011
	0.70	12.210	89.35	12.210	0.000
	2.50	6.105	44.72	6.115	+0.010
	2.50	12.210	89.40	12.210	0.000
	4.00	6.105	44.65	6.101	-0.004
	4.00	12.210	89.52	12.230	+0.020
	9.00	6.105	44.69	6.107	+0.002
	9.00	12.210	89.37	12.210	0.000

1 ml, $1.147 \times 10^{-2} M$ Palladium Chloride solution = 1.221 mg. Pd.

(C) Behaviour of (I) and (II) towards some other metallic ions :

To the solution of different metal salts ($1 \times 10^{-3} M$) an excess of the alcoholic solution of I or II was added. The pH values were adjusted as before. The results are summarised in Table 2.

TABLE 2—REACTIONS OF BENZOYL HYDROZONES OF I AND II WITH METALLIC IONS

Ion	Colour of ppt. or solution	pH of incipient ppt.	Behaviour of ppt.
Cu(II)	Greenish yellow	5.1	Insoluble in excess dil. alkali.
Ni(II)	Light yellow ppts.	7.0	Soluble in alkali and red ppts. at pH 8 to 9 are obtained.
Co(III)	Brownish yellow solution.	7.3	—
Fe(II)	Violet solution	6.0	On addition of excess alkali violet colour discharges giving dirty green ppts., probably $Fe(OH)_2$.
Fe(III)	Brownish yellow solution.	3.2	—

(D) Determination of Pd(II) in presence of cations :

In order to study the effect of other cations, Pd(II) was estimated in presence of 10 or 20 ml of Cu(II) and Ni(II) solutions at pH 0.5-0.9 by following the procedure described in A. The results are given in Tables 3A and 3B.

TABLE 3A—EFFECT OF Cu(II) AND Ni(II) ON THE DETERMINATION OF Pd(II)

Reagent : α -oximinoacetoacetanilide benzoyl hydrazone					
(a) pH of the medium	Pd(II) taken mg.	Cu(II) added mg.	Pd(II) chelate obtained mg.	Pd(II) found mg.	Error mg.
0.5-0.9	6.105	6.354	43.15	6.111	+0.006
"	6.105	12.708	43.06	6.105	0.000
"	6.105	6.354	43.08	6.105	0.000
"	6.105	12.708	43.10	6.110	+0.005
"	12.210	6.354	86.07	12.200	-0.010
"	12.210	12.708	86.10	12.210	0.000
"	12.210	6.354	86.05	12.200	-0.010
"	12.210	12.708	86.09	12.210	0.000
(b) pH of the medium	Pd(II) taken mg.	Ni(II) added mg.	Pd(II) chelate obtained mg.	Pd(II) found mg.	Error mg.
0.5-0.9	6.105	6.30	36.00	6.091	-0.014
"	6.105	12.60	36.20	6.123	+0.018
"	6.105	6.30	36.12	6.110	+0.005
"	6.105	12.60	36.10	6.108	+0.003
"	12.210	6.30	72.20	12.210	0.000
"	12.210	12.60	72.23	12.210	+0.010
"	12.210	6.30	72.25	12.220	+0.010
"	12.210	12.60	72.21	12.210	0.000

1 ml, 0.01M Copper Chloride solution = 0.6354 mg. Cu.
1 ml, 0.1073M Nickel Chloride solution = 0.63 mg. Ni.

TABLE 3B—EFFECT OF Cu(II) AND Ni(II) ON THE DETERMINATION OF Pd(II)

Reagent: α -oximinoacetoacet-o-toluidide benzoyl hydrazone.

(a) pH of the medium	Pd(II) taken mg.	Cu(II) added mg.	Pd(II) chelate obtained mg.	Pd(II) found mg.	Error mg.
0.5-0.9	6.105	6.354	44.71	6.113	+0.008
„	6.105	12.708	44.65	6.101	-0.004
„	6.105	6.354	44.50	6.090	-0.015
„	6.105	12.708	44.74	6.115	+0.010
„	12.210	6.354	89.41	12.220	+0.010
„	12.210	12.708	89.52	12.230	+0.020
„	12.210	6.354	89.37	12.210	0.000
„	12.210	12.708	89.53	12.230	+0.020

(b) pH of the medium	Pd(II) taken mg.	Ni(II) added mg.	Pd(II) chelate obtained mg.	Pd(II) found mg.	Error mg.
0.5-0.9	6.105	6.30	44.50	6.090	-0.015
„	6.105	12.60	44.73	6.115	+0.010
„	6.105	6.30	44.62	6.094	-0.011
„	6.105	12.60	44.65	6.101	-0.004
„	12.210	6.30	89.35	12.210	0.000
„	12.210	12.60	89.37	12.210	0.000
„	12.210	6.30	89.42	12.220	+0.010
„	12.210	12.60	89.53	12.230	+0.020

Results and Discussion

The results (Table 1) show that Pd(II) could be quantitatively estimated over a wide pH range, 0.7 to 10 in the absence of other metal ions. The pH values of incipient precipitation (Table 2) for metal ions viz., Cu(II), Ni(II), Fe(II) and Fe(III) suggest that in the presence of such metal ions palladium(II) could be estimated below pH, 3. A detailed study of quantitative estimation of palladium in presence of Cu(II) and Ni(II) has shown that Pd(II) could be estimated quantitatively in the pH range 0.5-0.9 (Tables 3A and 3B).

Complete precipitation, insolubility in common organic solvents and easy filtration of the complexes favour the use of these reagents as good gravimetric reagents for Pd(II). These characteristics are comparable with those of the standard method for the determination of palladium with dimethylglyoxime⁴.

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